

Moderating Role Of Board Size And Its Effect On Default Risk And Earning Response Coefficient (ERC)

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: April 29, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: July 25, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Board size and its effect on Default risk and ERC, Mitigating role of board size on Default Risk and ERC, Board size and ERC, default risk and Board Size</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5136514</p>	<p><i>This research explored the mitigating role of board size in the relationship between default risk and Earning Response Coefficient (ERC). The study selected 250 non financial companies listed in Pakistan stock exchange (PSX) from the period between 2008 to 2015. The statistical result shows that all determinants (Growth, Size and Earning Persistence) are positively related to ERC except Beta which means that Beta is considered a partial measure of risk relevant to ERC. The relationship between Default Risk and ERC is negative and significant. As for as mitigating role of board size is concerned, the result confirmed the hypothesis that board size plays a significant role to mitigate the negative relationship between default risk and earning Response coefficient (ERC). It also implies that large board size ensures better undertaking to monitor and control the excessive debts obligations which may protect the company from default risk and hence in turn positive affect on ERC. This study has great contribution and importance for literature and society of emerging economies because this study is investigated in emerging economy of Pakistan while previous studies mostly conducted in developed economies.</i></p>

Introduction

Board size is considered one of the significant factors of corporate Governance which plays an importance role to communicate required information between managers and investors. One of the important contributions of large board size is accessibility to capital market and better arrangement of monitoring all sorts of activities of a firm (Lehn et al, 2009; Phillips and Sipahioglu, 2004).

Fama(1980) stated that firm performance mostly depend on board of directors because they are directly involved in all sort of activities on behalf of owners. Hermalin and Weisbach (2003) argued that the firm efficiency mostly depend on small board size instead of large board size. An organization most of the agency problems raises due to large board size because it's become difficult to agree on one point. But Dalton and Dalton (2005) opinion is that large board size has multi skills, expertise, knowledge and capabilities which can play an important role to increase the ERC.

The ERC basically shows the response of investors towards stocks and investors are keenly interested to invest such stock where they have greater chances of high return. Profit margin is basic element of stock where investors can attract easily. There exist a close relationship between security and return and price of such security fluctuate very rapidly whose return are high. ERC plays a significant role to enhance the values of stocks. Investors can easily judge the companies and can make their investment decision by keeping in view the published information in the shape of income statement and balance sheet which represent the company financial position and performance in a specific period (Shah & Hussain, 2016; Hasanzade et al., 2014). ERC has four determinants.

The most important and significant determinates of ERC are Beta, growth, size and earning persistence are. These determinants play a significant role to predict the security return before investment decision Raza et al. (2018). It has been found that systematic risk is measure through beta and the relationship between beta and ERC is negative and significant. The same work is investigated more and found that as beta increases the ERC will decreases which mean that inverse relation exist between these two variables (Siregar & Maksum, 2018). It was also found that growth opportunities of such companies will be high whose profit margin increases time to time and it will positively affect the ERC. The consistency that how lengthy the companies earnings will remain continue in the future is termed as earning persistence. The investors are keenly interested to invest such sort of companies because they are expecting to get high return in future and ERC of such companies will also high. The size of the firm are defined through different ways like some are argued that total assets or capital represent the size while some says that total income shows the size of the firm (Andini & Sukartha, 2020).

Default risk arises when firm become unable to pay its obligation. Various models have been adopted to predict risk like Altman Z score (1966) and debt to equity ratio. According to Garlappi (2008) who stated that debts and default risk has strong link to one another, because low default risk firms can easily approach to debts while high default risk firms has low access to debts. An (2015) worked to find the relation between ERC and default risk. The proxy used for default risk as debt to equity ratio to find the hypothesis whether negative relationship exist between ERC and default risk. Lastly it was decided that a negative and significant relation exist between default risk and ERC.

The negative relationship between default risk and ERC can be mitigated through Board size, because different directors have different mind skill, capabilities, knowledge, skill and potentials through which they can better monitors and utilize the resources of organization in a better way which will decline the hazards of default risk and rise the ERC. Previous studies (Zakaria, 2013, Collins, 1994) also conducted same nature of studies and found consistent result.

Literature Review

Board Size:

Boards of directors are the key personalities to take important decision and action on behalf of shareholders. They have the authority to evaluate the performance of CEOs and Executives; moreover firm performance can greatly effect by board size. Argenti, (1976) Michael C Jensen (1993) stated that board is considered inefficient and firms are considered failure if the firm is not (a) properly implementing its policies, (b) no rules regulation to monitors employees works, (c) no standard rules for audit process, (d) lack of proper utilization of funds and internal policies.

Different researchers have different opinion about board size, some are in favor of small board though others are oppose. Lipton and Lorsch (1999) claimed that the more suitable board size for the better performance of a firm should be seven to eight, if board size is increasing from this limit, then it's difficult to control. It's difficult to unite a big board size on one point for the best interest of the firm, because everyone has different opinions, skills, calibers and expertise, which raise agency problem and lack of cohesiveness on the board. Dalton and Dalton (2005) indicated that large board size has the capabilities to enhance ERC due to multi skill, capabilities, expertise and knowledge.

Earning Response Coefficient (ERC)

The ERC basically shows the response of investors towards stocks and investors are keenly interested to invest such stock where they have greater chances of high return. Profit margin is basic element of stock where investors can attract easily. There exist a close relationship between security and return and price of such security fluctuate very rapidly whose return are high. ERC plays a significant role to enhance the values of stocks. Investors can easily judge the companies and can make their investment decision by keeping in view the published information in the shape of income statement and balance sheet which represent the company financial position and performance in a specific period (Shah & Hussain, 2016; Hasanzade et al., 2014). ERC has four determinants.

Beta

Systematic risk can be measured through Beta and there exist a negative and significant relationship between beta and ERC. Previous researchers also investigated and found the same result (zakaria, 2012).

Growth

Hasanzade et al. (2014) conducted a research and argued that chances of growth opportunities and ERC will increase as the profit margin increases. While other perception is that profit has no link with growth opportunities and ERC (Palupi, 2006).

Earning Persistence

Earning persistence means that how long the stock earnings will remains endure or continue in the coming future because earning persistence stock has more attraction and investors desire to invest such stock. So the positive relationship of stock return and earning persistence will greatly affect the ERC (Abousamak, 2018).

Firm size

According to Ibhagui & Olokoyo (2018) who calculated and found that one firm may be greater than other on the basis of their total income, asset or capital. One view is that those companies whose size is big will share more data on company's site and investors can get the required information easily. So on the base of these feature big size firm has greater ERC (Naimah & Siddhartha, 2006). A reverse opinion is that size of the firm has no effect on investors' investment decision and ERC (Laila, 2013).

Default Risk

When the company becomes unable to pay its debts/liabilities to the creditors is termed as default risk. Nagel & Purnanandam (2020) argued that those firms whose assets become less than its

liabilities/debts obligation, such firms are considered in default risk. The Cathcart et al. (2020) investigated a study to find the effect of financial leverage on ERC. Their results revealed that the effect of debt ratio on ERC is negative and significant. Hatchondo et al. (2016) also examined the relationship between ERC and default risk of debts while taking accounting earning and stock return as proxies of ERC. Their results suggested a negative and significant relation between default risk and ERC. Similarly, Ali et al. (2018) also investigated the same work and found that low growth and high debts ration is negatively related to ERC.

Mitigating Role of Board Size in the relationship between Default Risk and Earning Response Coefficient (ERC).

Board size plays an important role to mitigate the negative relationship between default risk and ERC, because different directors have different mind skill, capabilities, knowledge, and potentials through which they can better monitors and utilize the resources of organization in a better way which will decline the hazards of default risk and increase the ERC. Previous studies (Zakaria, 2013, Collins, 1994) also conducted same nature of research and found consistent result. so this implies that in corporate governance facet, board size is considered a significant facet because investors want a safe invest where chances of default is very low, and return proportion is high, and all these features are possible when corporate governance facet(Board size) monitors all sort of activities in every step of a company.

H1:Significant relation exist between default risk and Earning Response Coefficient (ERC)

H10:Insignificant relation exist between default risk and Earning Response Coefficient (ERC)

H2:Board size has a significant role to mitigate the negative relationship between default risk and Earning Response Coefficient (ERC).

H20:Board size has insignificant role to mitigate the negative relationship between default risk and Earning Response Coefficient (ERC).

Research Methodology

Study Period and Sample Selection:

Population of the study is non-financial firms listed in Pakistan Stock Exchange (PSX). The sample size of the study is 250 firms selected through purposive sample technique from the period 2008-2015. Annual reports, balance sheet analysis and companies own site used as a source of gathering the required data of the firms.

Statistical Tools for Data Analysis

Various statistical tools has been used to passed the gathered data for statistical analysis

Model Specification:

$$UR = ERC * (UX/P)$$

The ERC is represented through different variables i.e x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n which truly denote ERC

Then

$$UR = (x_1, x_2 \dots x_n) * (UX/P)$$

In UR regression, the Coefficient $X_i * (UX/P)$ on $\{X_i * (UX/P)\}$ is basically displays the outcome of X_i on ERC. In this model reverse regression will be used for estimation purpose as a substitute of direct regression because of measurement error in UR (Collins & Kothari, 1989). The $\{X_i\}$ effect is tested through regression on the basis of following technique.

$$UX/P = [1 / (x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n)] / UR$$

The above stated equation shows the regression equation.

$$UX/P = a_0 + a_1 UR + a_2 UR * X_1 + a_3 UR * X_2 + \dots + a_{n+1} UR * X_n + \varepsilon$$

The ERC turn to RRC (Return response coefficient) by applying reverse regression. Its means that the statistical results will react reverse.

The effect of X_i on ERC is due to the coefficient $\{X_i\}$ as it's discussed earlier, so the variable $\{X_i\}$ and to check the effect of Beta, firm Size, Earning Persistence and Growth, regression analysis will be used. Hypothesis 1, a negative and significant relation exists between default risk and ERC. In the set of $\{X_i\}$ the measure of default risk has been used in equation. The equation after this is as under.

$$UX/P = a_0 + a_1 UR + a_2 UR * DER + a_3 UR * BETA + a_4 UR * GRWTH + a_5 UR * EPRS + a_6 UR * SZ + \varepsilon$$

The default risk will show negative effect on ERC when $a^2 > 0$ while controlling ERC determinants. Hypothesis 2, Board Size mitigates the relationship between default risk and ERC. The following regression expression will be formed by adding the audit committee interaction with $UR * DER$.

$$UX/P = a_0 + a_1UR + a_2UR*DER + a_3UR*DER*BS + a_4UR*BETA + a_5UR*GROWTH + a_6UR*EPERS + a_7UR*SIZE + \varepsilon$$

Therefore, when the sign $\hat{\beta}_3 < 0$ and significant will indicate that Board Size (BS) mitigates the consequence of default risk on ERC.

Measurement of Variables:

Unexpected Earnings:

The unexpected earnings may be define as the EPS of current year minus previous year EPS.

Unexpected Return:

The proxy of unexpected return (UR) is Cumulative Abnormal Return (CAR) which is obtained from firms annual reports. The change between real and predictable return is termed as Abnormal return while estimation of expected return of a firm is obtain through sharp market model (1963).

Data Analysis

Descriptive Statistics

The study selected 250 no financial firms through purposive sampling technique and all these firms are listed in PSX. The study used secondary data available on companies own sites which is issued by state bank of Pakistan. Total observation were 2000 but 1697 were left after removing the outliers.

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics ofERC and Board size

Variable	Obs	Mean	Std. Dev	Min.	Max
Uxp	1696	0.16852	1.42201	-4.4594	9.36207
Beta	1697	0.59151	0.47861	-0.1683	1.90628
Sz	1697	14.1933	1.56920	10.3188	19.2531
Grth	1697	0.90627	0.94754	-1.8797	4.91668
Eprs	1697	2.69676	9.35631	-34.971	34.6435
Car	1697	0.06010	0.87624	-1.1230	4.40487
Bsz	1697	7.95041	1.40665	7	13
Der	1697	0.53078	1.20198	-4.298	6.53683

TheUxp (Unexpected Earning to price) mean and standard deviation value are0.16852 and1.42201 respectively. Similarly, 0.5915 is the mean value of beta and the market beta value is 1.0 which is almost half of the value. Its shows that the selected companies of the study have average low systematic risk assessment to the whole market. Thestandard deviation of beta value is 0.47861 which indicate that in the scattering of beta values the dispersion is quite low. The firm size and standard deviation mean value is 15.1933and 1.56920. Similarly, 0.90627 is firm mean value which shows that due to high growth prospective capabilities the stocks prices goes up and investors is still ready to pay this high price in the market. The average value and standard deviation of earnings persistence is 2.69676 and 9.35631. TheCAR mean value is 0.06010and its standard deviation is 0.87624.Likewise, mean value of DR (Default Risk) is 0.53077 which is moderate in comparison to minimum and maximum values given in the table. This suggests that comparatively, the sample companies on the average have moderate exposure to the default risk. The value also depicts that Pakistani Companies on the average have almost half level of debt financing than the equity financing.In result the average value of BS(Board size) is seven which means that an average there should be seven directors in the board size of a firm.

Correlation analysis:

Correlation was made to test all the variables. To show the relationship between two variables is expressed through Pearson correlation. In the following table all the value of pearson coefficient is less than .7(Alin, 2010) which means that there exist no issue of multicollinearity amongst the independent variables

the variables are statistically moderate and significant which means that all the independent variables has no serious issue of multicollinearity as all the value of pearson coefficient is less than .7(Alin,2010).

Correlation Matrix								
	Uxp	Bsz	Beta	Grth	Sz	Car	Eprs	Der
Uxp	1							
Bsz	-0.03	1						
Beta	0.027	0.166**	1					
Grth	-0.04	0.203**	0.028	1				
Sz	-0.056*	0.366**	0.199**	0.199	1			
Car	0.045	-0.026	0.116**	-0.0173	0.0447	1		
Eprs	-0.33**	-0.0244	-0.160**	-0.091**	-0.311**	-0.13	1	
Der	0.021	0.004	0.058	0.203**	0.105**	-0.008	0.05	1

ERC determinants Result

$$UX_{it}/P_{it} = \alpha_0 + a_1CAR_{it} + a_2CAR*BETA_{it} + a_3CAR*GRTH_{it} + a_4CAR*EPRS_{it} + a_5CAR*SZ_{it} + \text{Year fixed effect} + \epsilon_{it} \quad (1)$$

Dependent Variable UX/P

Pool OLS Regression DV=UX/P			Robust Pool		RE		FE		VIF
Variables	beta	P-value	beta	P-value	beta	P-value	beta	P-value	
Car	2.1594	0.0000	2.1594	0.0010	2.1594	0.0000	1.9078	0.0000	1.20
Carbeta	0.3644	0.0000	0.3644	0.0640	0.3644	0.0000	0.3155	0.0020	3.14
Cargrth	-0.0959	0.0400	-0.0959	0.2070	-0.0959	0.0600	-0.0974	0.0500	2.57
Careprs	-0.0192	0.0000	-0.0192	0.0200	-0.0192	0.0000	-0.0201	0.0010	1.15
Carsz	-0.1410	0.0000	-0.1410	0.0010	-0.1410	0.0000	-0.1221	0.0000	1.34
_cons	0.1466	0.0100	0.1466	0.0000	0.1466	0.0000	0.1469	0.0000	
R2	0.0342		0.0342		0.0342		0.0337		
Adjusted R2	0.0308								
F-value	9.9700		3.2500		59.8500		7.8100		
P-value	0.0000		0.0035		0.0000		0.0000		
Lamgre					0.0000	1.000			
Hausman test							5.74 (0.04525)		
Breusch –pagan							2.39 (0.53)		
Swilk							1.66 (0.78)		
Durbin Watson							2.175		

The statistical result shows that coefficient of CAR and Beta is linked positively and significantly which means that according to reverse regression the relationship between beta and ERC is negative and insignificant. Previous studies also found the same result (Chen et al., 2019). Similarly, The interaction of all other determinants of ERC (Growth, Size and Earning Persistence) with CAR are negatively and insignificantly related but due to reverse regression these all determinants are positively and significantly interlined with ERC. Earlier studies also conducted on same variables and extracted the same results (Raza et al., 2018; Zakaria, 2012; Shanguan, 2007)

Earning Response Coefficient (ERC) determinants result with default risk (DER)

$$UX_{it}/P_{it} = \alpha_0 + a_1CAR_{it} + a_2CAR*DER_{it} + f(\text{control variables}) + \epsilon_{it} \quad (2)$$

Dependent Variable UX/P

Pool OLS Regression DV=UX/P			Robust Pool		RE		FE		VIF
Variables	beta	P-value	beta	P-value	beta	P-value	beta	P-value	VIF
Car	0.069	0.110	0.069	0.342	0.069	0.109	0.076	0.098	1.36
Cardr	0.151	0.004	0.135	0.163	0.135	0.004	0.112	0.032	1.34
Beta	0.211	0.003	0.211	0.028	0.211	0.003	0.148	0.013	1.11
Grth	-0.120	0.001	-0.120	0.001	-0.120	0.001	-0.023	0.057	1.08
Eprs	-0.054	0.000	-0.054	0.000	-0.054	0.000	-0.064	0.000	1.05
sz	-0.084	0.000	-0.084	0.000	-0.084	0.000	-0.577	0.000	1.16
Cons	1.565	0.000	1.565	0.000	1.565	0.000	9.212	0.000	
R2	0.132		0.132		0.132		0.057		
Adjusted R2	0.130								
F-value	43.270		28.160		258.600		49.990		
P-value	0.000		0.000		0.000		0.000		
Lamgre					0.000	1.000			
Hausman test							61.84(0.000)		
Breusch-pagan							1.24 (0.24)		
Swilk							1.54 (0.30)		
Durbin Watson							2.237		

In the above table, the result shows a positive and insignificant relationship between CAR and default risk but due to reverse regression the result become opposite which means that the relationshi between Default risk and ERC is negative and significant. In this table all other determinants of ERC (Growth, size and earning

Pool OLS Regression DV=UX/P			Robust Pool		RE		FE		VIF
Variables	beta	P-value	beta	P-value	beta	P-value	beta	P-value	VIF
Car	0.067	0.117	0.067	0.345	0.067	0.117	0.076	0.099	1.37
Cardr	0.055	0.684	0.055	0.789	0.055	0.684	0.147	0.337	1.12

persistence) are linked positively and significantly except Beta and the same result pertaining to Default Risk (DR), ERC and ERC Determinants are also found by others researchers (Assagafet al., 2019; Zakaria, 2012; Cheng and Nasir, 2010; Shangguan, 2007).

The negative and significant result between default risk and ERC indicates that ERC will decrease as the default risk increase and vice versa. So the Hypothesis 1 is strongly supported: which state that a negative and significant relation exists between default risk and ERC.

The mitigating role of board Size on the relationship between default risk and ERC

$$UX_{it}/P_{it} = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 CAR_{it} + \alpha_2 CAR_{it} * DER_{it} + \alpha_3 CAR_{it} * DER_{it} * BSZ_{it} + f(\text{control variables}) + \epsilon_{it}(3)$$

Dependent Variable UX/P

CarderBsz	-0.169	0.013	-0.042	0.025	-0.042	0.013	-0.029	0.032	3.32
Beta	0.207	0.004	0.207	0.030	0.207	0.004	0.148	0.031	1.12
Grth	-0.120	0.001	-0.120	0.001	-0.120	0.001	-0.023	0.058	1.08
Eprs	-0.054	0.000	-0.054	0.000	-0.054	0.000	-0.064	0.000	1.05
Sz	-0.083	0.000	-0.083	0.000	-0.083	0.000	-0.577	0.000	1.16
R2	0.133		0.133		0.133		0.058		
Adjusted R2	0.130								
F-value	37.130		24.170		259.910		42.810		
P-value	0.000		0.000		0.000		0.000		
Lamgre					0.000	1.000			
Hausman test							62.81 (0.000)		
Breusch-pagan							1.23 (0.29)		
Swilk							1.21 (0.71)		
Durbin Watson							2.112		

The test result depict that positive and insignificant association exist amongst the The interaction of CAR, DER and BSZ but due to reverse regression the result is opposite which means that a negative and significant relationship exist between the interaction of DR , BSZ and its relation with ERC .Therefore, the hypothesis H2 is supported which stated that:Board size has a significant role to mitigate the negative relationship between default risk and Earning Response Coefficient (ERC).it suggest thatthe effects of default risk on ERC will decrease as the numbers of directors increases in the board. It also implies that large board size ensures better undertaking to monitor and control the excessive debts obligations which may protect the company from default risk and hence in turn positive affect on ERC.Nuriyanto et al. (2020) also found the consistent results that the existence of large numbers of board size will decrease the negative effect of default risk on ERC.

Conclusion

This study examined that how board size mitigate the negative effect between default risk and earnings response coefficient, while controlling all thedeterminants of ERC. The result shows that all the ERC determinants are positively and significantly interlinked to one another except beta. The results also depicts that a negative and significant association exist between default risk and ERC. Moreover the earning persistence will decrease as increase the default risk and hence in turn unexpected earnings will decrease the abnormal return of securities which will ultimately decrease the ERC. According to second hypothesis, Board size has a significant role to mitigate the negative relationship between default risk and ERC.Itsuggests thatthe effects of default risk on ERC will decrease as the numbers of board size increases It also implies that large board size ensures better undertaking to monitor and control the excessive debts obligations which may protect the company from default risk and hence in turn positive affect on ERC.Nuriyanto et al. (2020) also found the consistent results that the existence of large numbers of board size will decrease the negative effect of default risk on ERC.

Therefore asignificant facet of corporate governanceisboardsize which is free to judge and keep close observation to monitors all sort of activities of a firm without any pressure. In this way chances of debt obligation and default risk decrease which will ultimately increase ERC.This research is beneficial for those researchers who conduct their research in capital market and see the mitigating role of corporate governance variables on default risk and ERC determinants.

Recommendations

The recommendations of the study are as following.

- A strategy should be adopted to manage the systematic risk and better asset allocation.
- The regulatory authority should consider the size board as the board size of the firm plays an important role.
- Similarly, the companies may reduce their default risk and increase ERC through better corporate governance facets and efficient utilization of debts obligations and strong monitoring system where every transaction and activity of the company may properly check and monitor.
- The regulatory authority should increase the numbers of directors in board where they can improve the firm performance.

Future Directions

- Large sample size and longer time frame should be considered by future researchers.
- Similar researches can be performed in other emerging economies to verify the findings of this research.

- The researchers may refine and contribute towards the pertinent literature of this study by taking into account other determinants of ERC, Default risk and corporate governance facets. Researchers may conduct their studies by inter-relationship of variables and comparative analysis of emerging and developing economies of different countries

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